

TEACHING BRASS METHOD SWIMMING TECHNIQUES

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The Brass method involves adjusting the movements of the arms and legs in swimming and matching them with breathing and exhaling, initially under the number of the practitioners themselves or their teacher. Practical experiments in recent years in teaching this method "1", "2", "3" it was shown that it is advisable to apply the number. Those involved in the triple count correctly and quickly master the technique of limb movement as well as their adaptation to breathing and exhalation. It is necessary to start by taking the full movement of the foot, holding in the initial position the adjustment of the Coordination of the general movement with the release of the limb, taking free breathing. This position makes the hands of the practitioners accustomed to holding in the initial position. It is also necessary to fully exhale and maintain the acceleration of the torso from the leg depressions. In addition, it is necessary for those involved to move forward efficiently, getting used to the movement of the legs effectively. Once practitioners learn foot movement, they quickly and easily master foot and hand movements as usual, alternating, breath-contact. This makes it possible to properly acquire knowledge in this area of swimming.

The exercises to teach the technique of swimming in the Brass method are as follows:

On land:

I. 1. Running while learning foot movement techniques:

- turning the paws to the side, inward;
- walking the legs in different widths and positions, sitting half and full;

- it is necessary to sit down, jump and perform other preparatory exercises, as if swimming in the brass method.

Mastering these exercises improves mobility, creakiness in the paw-calf, calf-thigh joints of the foot. Those involved who have good mobility and agility in their boots master the special exercises that are given below correctly and quickly.

D.h. – sitting on the front edge (or ground) of the gymnastics bench, resting with the hands on the back edge, the legs are paired until the tip is stretched, and the paws are placed on the floor:

«1» legs are bent at the knees and hip joints and written at shoulder width (this movement is performed without straining the leg muscles and without removing the paw from the ground)

"2" – the ends of the leg are pulled into the hammer and turn to the side;

"3" – the legs are straightened from the groin, knee joints, in which each footpipe performs deprecation, forming an arc (side-in the back direction) (in which the soles of the feet are d.h. stretches only when it comes to).

2. D.h. – lying on a gymnastics bench with a chest, in a position with legs extended, leg movement "1", "2", "3" performed on a count (this exercise is performed first with the help of a partner, then independently).

3. D.h. - hanging on the tourniquet and extending the legs, "1", "2", "3" in the counting, the leg movement is performed.

4. D.h. – sitting on the edge of the pool, leaning back with hands, legs are extended, lowered into the water, "1", "2", "3" in the count, the action is performed.

II. When adjusting foot movement with Breath, exercise 2 above is used. In this case, on the " 1 "- count, the head is raised and inhaled, on the " 2 " - count, the head is d.h. returns to (down), in "3", breathing is exhaled during movement.

III. Exercises for teaching hand movement techniques:

1. D.h.- bent forward, facing down with the palm, paired arms are extended. In Measure"1", the hands are bent from the palms and elbow joints to perform the act of rowing in the lateral, downward, backward direction to the shoulder joint barrier, while

in Measure" 2", the hands are bent from the elbow joints, the shoulder is pinched. "3" -arms straightened, forward, d.h. are brought to. 2. The first exercise is performed Walking.

IV. When teaching breath adjustment to hand movement, the above task III exercises 1 and 2 are used.

In this, the " 1 "is exhaled with the head raised, while the" 2 " is exhaled with the head down (d.h. ga) return, exhaling during movement in "3".

V. Exercises to adjust the movement of the foot to the movement of the hand in the Brass method:

1. D.h.–stands upright, feet shoulder-width apart, paws facing sideways, arms paired with arms extended upwards over head:

"1", "2", "3"-hand movement is performed with a break of 2-3 seconds on the count;

"1", "2", "3"-a brass band sits on the bill.

2.D.h.- as in the first exercise.

In "1", while bending the legs and squatting, the hands perform a" rowing " movement, in "2"(in this exercise, the legs are motionless, and in the next–performed on the bench, the paws are pulled and turned to the side), the hands are bent over the elbow joint, the shoulder is pinched, in "3", the legs are straightened at the knee-elbow joints (depressing is performed), and the hands are adjusted at this time,h. returns to.

3.D.x. - lie transversely with the chest on the gymnastics bench. Extended with arms and legs paired: "1", "2", "3"-the number is preceded by the same movement as Exercise 1, followed by the same movement as Exercise 2.

VI. Exercises to train breathing in accordance with the technique of hand-foot movement in the Brass method. In teaching this, exercises 2 and 3 in the previous task V are used. In this case, the "1" in the performance of each exercise is exhaled, raising the head. Scope = "row" rowspan =" 2 " / head d.h.ga returns. A breathing adjustment exercise is performed on movements in "3".

Proper and thorough study of land exercises will help you quickly learn the swimming method in the water.

In the water:

I. Learning exercises to practice leg movement techniques with free breathing and without exhaling:

1. Holding hands on the edge of the pool from a special handle, the legs are extended towards the shore, lying on the chest (back), the leg movement is performed.

On the " 1 " - count, bend the legs from the knee and groin joints and pull to the two sides;

In " 2 " - the paws are pulled to the shin and the side is pulled, there is a groin and a knee, the legs are pulled;

In " 3 " - the act of rowing is performed, recording the legs at the same time from the groin and knee joints.

2. With the help of foot movement, the pool is transverse as follows:

a) Without exhaling, depressing from the pool wall, placing the head in the water with the surface, patching the fingers of the hand and pointing the palms down, transmitted forward;

b) depress from the pool wall, holding hands near the torso, lowering the head with the surface into the water, and sliding with the breath in hand;

d) holds a tablet in the hands and swims in positions where he breathes freely.

II. Breathing exercise. Breathing by raising the head up, lowering the head with a bet and exhaling inside the water is performed in the following situations:

1. In the shallow part of the pool, it is performed with half-bending forward, placing the hands on the knee, and the hands with the palms of the hands clasped and extended, or holding the hands near the torso.

2. It is performed by tilting the arm towards the shore and holding a special handle on the edge of the pool.

III. Exercises to adapt and master the technique of foot movement with breathing:

1. D.h. – lying on the chest, with one hand he is grabbed by a special handle, with the other he rests under the water on the pool wall, the legs are properly extended, with the "1"-the head back and forth, exhaled, on the "2"-the legs are bent, pulled back, brought to the position of the ass (preparatory movement), on the "3" –

It is necessary that the handlers exhale in the water before starting the act of rowing, lowering the head with the surface into the water, while the feet perform the act of rowing. After that, they need to start breathing and finish it on the "two" count.

2. By adjusting the breath to the foot movements to the width and height of the pool:

(a) holding the tablet straight in the arms;

b) the palms of the hands without a tablet are stretched forward (the hands are extended along the torso), directed downward. In order to improve the technique of leg movement, to eliminate the errors that occur in it, Exercise 2, it is recommended to repeat a, b in a back position.

IV. Exercises to train and master the technique of hand movement in accordance with the release of breath with free breathing:

1. The torso is half-bent forward in the shallow part of the pool, with a paired palm facing down, the arms are extended forward. The breath is free in "1", the hands are backward, in "2", the hands are bent, in "3", the hands return to the initial position. Previous exercises are matched with breathing: "1" is inhaled, "2" is inhaled and exhaled, "3" is exhaled.

2. When swimming by lightly moving the foot in the crook or dolphin method to the width and neck of the pool, the hand movement is performed by adjusting it with the breath.

V. Breathing adjustment exercises for ARM and leg movement.

1. The movements of the arms and legs are performed separately, alternating, breathing is not released in the swing, the arms are paired and the palm is extended forward, facing down. The legs are paired and properly extended, the head is lowered into the water with the surface; in "1", the act of rowing and preparation with the hands

is performed, in "2", the act of rowing and preparation with the legs is performed.

The previous exercise is aligned with the breath: "1" is inhaled, "2" is exhaled.

2. Hand and foot movements are adjusted:

a) when sliding without exhaling, the arms are paired, pointing down with the palm and extended forward. The legs are extended in pairs, the head is lowered into the water with a surface. "1" - the act of rowing with the hands is performed, "2" - the hands are bent, the preparatory movement is performed with the legs, "3" - the hands return to the initial position, the legs perform the act of rowing;

b) the previous exercise is aligned with the breath: "1" is inhaled by raising the head from the water; "2" is exhaled by raising the head; "3" is exhaled by completing the breath and exhaling; "3" is preceded by a full leg movement and exhaling at the same time as the head bet into the water, and then hand movement begins and exhales.

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